

Recent results from LHCb on charged-current decays of b -hadron

Patrizia de Simone *¹

¹INFN Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati, Via Enrico Fermi 40, 00044, Frascati, Italy

On behalf of the LHCb Collaboration

Abstract

The Lepton Flavour Universality described within the Standard Model is challenged by persistent tensions on charged-current semileptonic decays of b -hadrons. The ratios $\mathcal{R}(D)$ and $\mathcal{R}(D^*)$ show a combined discrepancy with predictions of over three standard deviations. This proceeding presents recent results of lepton flavour universality tests and kinematical studies in $b \rightarrow c l \nu$ decays, using hadronic or muonic τ decays, performed at LHCb.

1 Introduction

The semileptonic b -hadron decays, which proceed via charged-current interactions, provide a suitable laboratory to test the Standard Model (SM) and to search effects of possible New Physics (NP) by measures devoted to determine the CKM matrix elements V_{ub} and V_{cb} , to test the Lepton Flavour Universality (LFU) and to study the kinematic of the final state particles.

The variables commonly used to test the LFU are ratios of decay rates between the semitauonic and the semimuonic b -hadrons channels. The HFLAV averaging group keeps updated the combination of the measured ratios $\mathcal{R}(D^{(*)}) = \mathcal{BR}(B \rightarrow D^{(*)} \tau \nu_\tau) / \mathcal{BR}(B \rightarrow D^{(*)} \mu \nu_\mu)$ that shows a significant long-standing tension with the SM predictions, presently at the level of 3.8σ [1].

The following proceedings present an update of the LHCb physics program devoted to improve the precision on $\mathcal{R}(D)$ and $\mathcal{R}(D^*)$, adding new LFU tests with different b -hadrons and studying the kinematic of these semileptonic decays. After a concise description of the experimental and analysis techniques to select the semileptonic decays at LHCb, we report the recent measurement of $\mathcal{R}(D^+)$ and $\mathcal{R}(D^{*+})$, the first evidence of the $B \rightarrow D^{**} \tau \nu_\tau$ decay and the measurement of the D^* longitudinal polarization in the $\bar{B}^0 \rightarrow D^{*+} \tau^- \bar{\nu}_\tau$ decays.

2 Detection of the b -hadron semileptonic decays at LHCb

The LHCb [2], [3] detector records data at the LHC, where the b quarks are produced through gluon fusion and thus all b -hadron species are created: B^+ , B^0 , B_s^0 , B_c^+ and Λ_b^0 .

The b -hadrons, H_b , are strongly boosted, which provides an excellent separation between production and decay vertices. Thanks to the excellent performance of the LHCb vertex detector, the flight direction of the H_b is measured with good precision from which the transverse momentum of the neutrino from the semimuonic H_b channels, can be deduced up to a twofold ambiguity [4]. The semitauonic b -hadrons channels are selected looking for the fully leptonic or hadronic τ decays, the relative procedures to evaluate the missing momentum of the ν_τ are different [5]:

*Presenting author.

- $\tau \rightarrow \mu\nu_\mu\nu_\tau$: the procedure, named Rest Frame Approximation (RFA), assumes that the proper velocity of the H_b along the beam axis is the same as that of the reconstructed visible final state, the selected pair of a c -hadron, H_c , and a muon. In the highly boosted regime of LHCb, the RFA is a good approximation that leads to a resolution on the squared 4-momentum transferred to the lepton pair, q^2 , of about 22%.
- $\tau \rightarrow \pi\pi\pi\nu(\pi^0)$: in the highly boosted regime of LHCb the H_b and the τ vertices are well separated and both their flight directions can be measured with good precision, allowing to evaluate the missing momentum up to a fourfold ambiguity, resulting in a overall q^2 resolution of about 19%.

The selection of the $H_c\mu$ pairs collect large amount of background from partially reconstructed H_b decays mainly due to inclusive semileptonic decays (feed-down), such as the $B \rightarrow D^{**}\tau\nu_\tau$ decays, and to the double charm decays where one of the c -hadron decays semileptonically. Multivariate analysis techniques are heavily used to reject backgrounds where an additional track can be associated to the signal, the $H_c\mu$ pair. Such techniques are used also to select enriched background samples used to constrain the final fit.

Histogram templates are used to model the final selected data sample, which is composed of the semitauonic signal, the semimuonic normalization and the different sources of background. The background components due to hadrons mis-identified as muons and to combinatorial are modelled with templates based on data control samples. Signal, normalization and physics backgrounds are described with templates based on simulation, and these are dependent on the form factor parametrization used at the generation level. The **HAMMER** software tool [6] is used

- for an efficient event-by-event reweighting to different form factor models;
- implemented in a **Roofit-Hammer** interface [7] or in a python tool **Redist-Hammer** [8] to vary the form factor parameters during the final fit procedure.

To conclude, the size of the simulated samples used to fill the histogram templates limits the final precision of the measurements; this explains the great effort put into several fast simulation options that have been made available or are under development at LHCb [9].

3 Probing LFU in B meson decays

The first LHCb simultaneous measurement of $\mathcal{R}(D^+)$ and $\mathcal{R}(D^{*+})$ [10], done with a dataset of 2 fb^{-1} collected at $\sqrt{s}=13 \text{ TeV}$, measures the ratios

$$\mathcal{R}(D^{+(*)}) = \mathcal{BR}(\bar{B}^0 \rightarrow D^{+(*)}\tau^-\bar{\nu}_\tau) / \mathcal{BR}(\bar{B}^0 \rightarrow D^{+(*)}\mu^-\bar{\nu}_\mu) \quad (1)$$

where the τ lepton is selected via the $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \bar{\nu}_\mu \nu_\tau$ decay mode, and with the $D^{*+} \rightarrow D^+\pi^0$ and the $D^+ \rightarrow K\pi\pi$ decays. The two measurements are done selecting the same visible final state, three charged hadrons and one muon. An isolation tool for charged tracks is used to split the selected data into signal and normalization sample, and three control samples with enhanced sensitivity to the background components, after which the yields of the semitauonic and semimuonic B^0 decays are determined with a simultaneous fit across the four data samples. The fit is a three-dimensional template fit to the energy of the muon in the B meson rest frame, E_μ^* , the squared missing mass, m_{miss}^2 , and q^2 . Figure 1 shows the fit result overlaid to the E_μ^* and m_{miss}^2 distributions for values within the highest q^2 bin, $[9.44, 11.8] \text{ GeV}^2/c^4$, where the contribution due to $\bar{B}^0 \rightarrow D^+\tau^-\bar{\nu}_\tau$ in orange and $\bar{B}^0 \rightarrow D^{*+}\tau^-\bar{\nu}_\tau$ in red, clearly shows up.

Figure 1: Distributions of m_{miss}^2 (left) and E_{μ}^* (right) in the highest q^2 bin of the selected data sample, overlaid with the projections of the fit model. The signal components are drawn in red and orange, while the semimuonic decays in blue and light-blue. Background components of the selected samples are the doubly charmed decays in grey, the feed-down decays in violet, combinatorial and misidentified muons in yellow.

The ratios are evaluated correcting the yields for the selection efficiencies, evaluated with simulated corrected samples, and for the τ branching ratio [12]:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{R}(D^+) &= 0.249 \pm 0.043 \text{ (stat)} \pm 0.047 \text{ (syst)}, \\ \mathcal{R}(D^{*+}) &= 0.402 \pm 0.081 \text{ (stat)} \pm 0.085 \text{ (syst)},\end{aligned}$$

with a correlation of $\rho = -0.39$. The largest contributions to the systematic uncertainty are due to the form-factor parametrization and to the modelling of the background. The obtained values are compatible with the SM at the level of 0.78σ .

The first evidence of the $B \rightarrow D^{**} \tau \nu_{\tau}$ decay has been obtained using a dataset of 9 fb^{-1} collected at $\sqrt{s}=7, 8$ and 13 TeV , [11]. The main interest for this analysis comes from the need to clarify one of the largest systematic uncertainties common to all the $\mathcal{R}(D^{(*)})$ measurements: the feed-down contamination from excited D^{**} decays. The search includes all the charmed mesons more massive than the $D^*(2010)$ that decay in $D^* \pi$: $D_1(2420)$, $D_1^*(2400)$, and $D_2^*(2460)$. The semitauponic decays sample is collected with reconstructed $D^{**} \rightarrow D^* \pi$ and $D^* \rightarrow D^0 \pi$, while the τ in its hadronic channels: the selection follows the same strategy as a previous $\mathcal{R}(D^*)$ measurement by LHCb [13]. The $B \rightarrow D^{**} \tau \nu_{\tau}$ decay has been observed with a significance of 3.5σ . Using the branching fraction of the normalization channel $\mathcal{BR}(B^- \rightarrow D_{1,2}^{**0} D_s^{(*)}) = (0.27 \pm 0.05)\%$ [14], where $D_{1,2}^{**0}$ represents the combined contributions from the narrow states $D_1(2420)$, and $D_2^*(2460)$, the combined branching fraction is measured:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{BR}(B^- \rightarrow D_{1,2}^{**0} \tau^- \bar{\nu}_{\tau}) \times \mathcal{BR}(B^- \rightarrow D_{1,2}^{**0} D_s^{(*)}) &= \\ (0.051 \pm 0.013 \text{ (stat)} \pm 0.006 \text{ (syst)} \pm 0.009 \text{ (ext)})\% &,\end{aligned}$$

where the last uncertainty reflects that of the branching ratio of the normalization channel. Finally, using the world average values for the semimuonic decays in $D_1(2420)$, and $D_2^*(2460)$ [12], the LFU ratio is found to be $\mathcal{R}(D_{1,2}^{**0}) = 0.13 \pm 0.03 \text{ (stat)} \pm 0.01 \text{ (syst)} \pm 0.02 \text{ (ext)}$, in good agreement with the SM prediction of 0.09 ± 0.02 [15] [16] [17], and consistent with the assumptions made in the various $\mathcal{R}(D^{(*)})$ measurements. This implies that the observed deviation of $\mathcal{R}(D^{(*)})$ from the SM prediction is not likely to be due to a global underestimation of $B \rightarrow D^{**} \tau \nu_{\tau}$ decays.

Figure 2: Distributions of $\cos\theta_D$ in the (left) Run 1 and (right) Run 2 datasets, overlaid with the projections of the fit model. The signal components are drawn in red.

Studies of the kinematic and angular distributions, such as the longitudinal D^* polarization fraction, $F_L^{D^*}$, can provide additional sensitivity to possible NP scenarios [18]. LHCb performed an angular analysis of the $\bar{B}^0 \rightarrow D^{*+}\tau^-\bar{\nu}_\tau$ decay with the τ reconstructed in its hadronic mode [19], using a dataset of 5 fb^{-1} collected at $\sqrt{s}=7, 8$ and 13 TeV . The value of the $F_L^{D^*}$ observable is extracted from the angular distribution of the $D^{*-} \rightarrow D^0\pi^+$ decay, that is a function of q^2 and $\cos\theta_D$, where θ_D is the angle of the D^0 meson direction opposite to the B meson in the D^* rest frame. The $F_L^{D^*}$ is measured in two q^2 regions. Also the selection of this analysis follows the same strategy of [13]. Figure 2 shows the fit results overlaid to the $\cos\theta_D$ distributions for the two q^2 regions.

The D^* polarization fractions are given by the extracted yields of polarized and unpolarized signal splitting the simulated templates in two components, one completely unpolarized while the other fully polarized:

$$\begin{aligned} q^2 < 7 \text{ GeV}^2/c^4 : & \quad 0.51 \pm 0.07 \text{ (stat)} \pm 0.03 \text{ (syst)} , \\ q^2 > 7 \text{ GeV}^2/c^4 : & \quad 0.35 \pm 0.08 \text{ (stat)} \pm 0.02 \text{ (syst)} , \\ q^2 \text{ whole range} : & \quad 0.43 \pm 0.06 \text{ (stat)} \pm 0.03 \text{ (syst)} . \end{aligned}$$

These measurements are compatible with SM predictions and with the results obtained by the Belle experiment [20].

4 Conclusions

This proceeding has presented some aspects of the wide LHCb physics program on semileptonic charged-current decays. The presented measurements of $\mathcal{R}(D^+)$ and $\mathcal{R}(D^{*+})$ do not modify the tension between $\mathcal{R}(D^{(*)})$ HFLAV world average and the SM prediction. A potential explanation for this tension has been directly addressed: the feed-down contamination from semitauonic D^{**} decays has been evaluated confirming the assumptions made in all the $\mathcal{R}(D^{(*)})$ measurements. Finally the measurement of the D^* longitudinal polarization in the $\bar{B}^0 \rightarrow D^{*+}\tau^-\bar{\nu}_\tau$ decays, has been presented. The LHCb physics program on semileptonic charged-current decays is ongoing with many more analysis, to provide new LFU tests and constraints to physics beyond the SM. In addition, with the high-statistics dataset currently being collected in Run 3, LHCb will push further the precision of these measurements.

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